

Predicting the Parameters of the Output Flow of Conveyor Systems

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Abstract— In this article, the problem of constructing models of multi-section conveyor-type transport systems using a neural network is considered. The analysis of models of long-distance multi-section transport systems, which are used to design control systems of the flow parameters from the point of view of reducing the unit costs of material transportation, is presented. The areas of the models' application and associated limitations are demonstrated. The advantages of using neural networks for developing multi-section transport systems models are shown. The influence of the initial distribution of materials along the transport route and the presence of a transport delay in the system on the quality of predict of the transport system flow parameters are estimated. The effect of the use of speed sensors located on the inner and output sections in order to improve the quality of predict of the transport system flow parameters is analyzed. It is shown that the use of speed sensors in conveyors with belt speed control can significantly improve the quality of predict.

Keywords—multi-section conveyor, transport delay, PDE conveyor model, belt speed control, conveyor model, ANN, process efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

The key task directly related to the use of artificial intelligence in enterprises with a flow method of organizing production is mainly the task of operational management. Special attention is paid to this issue at mining enterprises [1], [2], in particular, to solve the problem of minimizing energy costs when transporting material from the place of production to the place of shipment. As the main means of transportation, a conveyor is used, which is one of the most economical ways of transporting material and allows you to move material through difficult terrain [3], [4], [5]. By a material loading factor of the transport section of 0.5–0.7 [6], transport costs are 20% of the total cost of the extracted material for a medium-length transport route (5–15 km) [7]. For the longest transport systems, the length of which usually reaches 100 km [8], the cost of transporting material increases in proportion to the length of the transport route. With an uneven loading of the transport system with the material, the load factor of the transport system can significantly decrease, that leads to a significant increase in the specific energy consumption by the material transportation per unit length. One of the ways to reduce energy consumption for the transportation process is increasing the level of material loading of the transport system [9]–[11]. It is achieved by using a control system for the material flow coming from the accumulating bunker to

the inlet of the conveyor section [12]–[14], the speed of the conveyor belt [15], or a combined control system. To construct control systems, conveyor models are most often used, which are based on the equations of system dynamics [14], the aggregated equation of state [16], Lagrange equations, finite element method [3], [17], [18]. Models containing Lagrange equations and the finite element method allow one to take into account the uneven distribution of material along the transportation route. However, when designing control systems for a multi-section transport conveyor, their use is difficult due to the high cost of computing resources. The development of an analytical model (PiKh-model) of the conveyor section [19] made it possible to design control systems for a multi-section conveyor [20]. However, if the number of sections reaches several tens, then the use of an analytical model also leads to computational difficulties [8]. One of the solutions to this problem is the use of a neural network and multiple regression equations to model the transport system. This article focuses on the development of the shown approach.

CONCLUSION

The use of artificial intelligence methods makes it possible to design information systems for the efficient management of multi-section transport conveyors. The use of artificial intelligence methods is of particular importance when constructing models of a transport network consisting of several tens or even hundreds of interconnected sections. In this case, analytical models cease to be attractive, and models containing the Lagrange equations, finite element method become simply difficult to implement for describing such transport systems. An effective solution in this case is the development of models of a multi-section transport system based on a neural network. At the same time, the use of various kinds of monitoring systems based on machine vision and digital image processing algorithms makes it possible to conduct training of a neural network quite effectively. This paper shows as the additional use of contactless belt speed sensors can significantly improve the accuracy of predicting the output flow parameters of a conveyor-type transport system. A further development of this research is the analysis of the application of systems for monitoring the parameters of the transport conveyor containing contactless sensors of the material flow. In contrast to the case of using belt speed sensors, when one sensor is enough to record the belt speed, several non-contact material flow sensors can be placed for a separate

section, which supposedly should significantly improve the accuracy of predicting the output parameters of the transport system. By in the same time, it is necessary to separately assess the increase in prediction accuracy associated with a change in the architecture of the neural network.

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